

The Italian project SUONO: preliminary results on underwater manipulation tasks

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Abstract—The demanded tasks for sub-sea operations have become progressively challenging as, for instance, intervention, maintenance and repair of seabed installations for the offshore industry. Motivated by these considerations, this paper presents an overview of the Italian SUONO (Safe Underwater Operations iN Oceans) project, which involves the Department of Industrial Engineering (DIEF) of the University of Florence, a node of the Italian Research Center on Integrated System for the Marine Environment (ISME), Italy, and four other Italian partners, from Academia as well as Industry. More in detail, the SUONO project aims to integrate technologies and methodologies to enable the development of autonomous underwater robotic systems employable for intervention activities, such as free-floating manipulation tasks on a sub-sea panel.

Index Terms—Marine Robotics, Underwater Intervention, Autonomous Underwater Manipulation Systems

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the past decades, several strategies and approaches have been developed as accomplishment solutions for autonomous underwater manipulation tasks [1] [2]. Motivated by these research activities, this paper presents an overview of the Italian SUONO (Safe Underwater Operations iN Oceans) project, which involves the Department of Industrial Engineering (DIEF) of the University of Florence, a node of the Italian Research Center on Integrated System for the Marine Environment (ISME), Italy, and four other Italian partners, from Academia as well as Industry. Building on the previous results, the challenge of developing underwater robotic systems for manipulation tasks is carried out by exploiting the well-known task-priority control approach [3]; additionally, gathering knowledge of the environment, as, for instance, accurately mapping an underwater scenario, represents a preliminary but surely fundamental hierarchical stage for effectively accomplishing interactive operations [4].

This paper is organized as follows. Section II summarizes the whole overview of the SUONO architecture, starting from the control framework to the involved perception module. Section III illustrates the preliminary experimental results obtained by several laboratory tests. Finally, Section IV highlights the presented research by focusing on the significant accomplished

results; moreover, a brief description of the future trends is presented.

II. THE SUONO PROJECT ARCHITECTURE

The proposed SUONO architecture, composed of several different blocks, is hereafter briefly illustrated (Fig. 1). The Perception System provides the map of the surrounding environment, along with the pose of the arm end-effector with respect to a target valve, by using a monocular visual Simultaneous Localization And Mapping (SLAM) algorithm [5], aided with Augmented Reality (AR) markers to solve the scale factor issue [6]. Additionally, this block provides an occupancy map of the scene [7] by exploiting the point cloud previously built. The desired end-effector pose, with respect to the detected valve, is supplied as input of the Kinematic Control Layer (KCL), based on the task-priority control framework [3]. The whole process, described above, is handled by the Mission Scheduler, which is in charge of supervising the execution of the current mission, and managing the interactivity between the Perception System and the KCL.

Fig. 1. The SUONO project procedural workflow for intervention tasks.

Switching from a kinematic to a dynamic hierarchical level, the reference velocities, generated by the KCL, are furtherly

used by the Dynamic Control Layer (DCL), which tracks the desired system velocity vector by employing the appropriate force/torques commands for the Underwater Vehicle Manipulator System (UVMS). While state-of-the-art dynamic controls of UVMS systems have been comprehensively detailed in the literature, this work focuses on describing the kinematic control and perception architectures employed within the context of the SUONO project.

III. PRELIMINARY RESULTS

The results of several laboratory experiments, in which an underwater robotic arm is controlled with the proposed control and perception architecture, are described in this section.

Fig. 2. The preliminary results obtained in several laboratory tests: the position and orientation errors of the arm end-effector converge to a null value.

The manipulator starting pose is set far away from the desired one estimated by the Perception System. As a result of the proposed control framework, the end-effector position and orientation error converge to zero, as shown in Fig. 2. Furthermore, Fig. 3 reports the preliminary mapping results performed by the Perception System on a simple panel mock-up developed in the context of the SUONO project.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE TRENDS

This paper presents the framework of the Italian SUONO project for underwater intervention tasks. Furthermore, the whole developed architecture has been validated, proving the

Fig. 3. View of the panel mock-up employed during the experiments (top-left image), vision-based 3D reconstruction of the panel (top-right image) and a 3D occupancy map built by the Perception System.

feasibility of the proposed approach, with preliminary laboratory experiments. The following steps will involve testing the proposed framework during on-field experimental campaigns in a real underwater scenario, and investigating the employment of AI-based methodologies to pave the way towards innovative underwater manipulation systems.

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